

A REVIEW ON MANAGEMET AND DIAGNOSIS OF ALCOHOLIC LIVER DISEASE

Dr.P.Kavitha¹, Agalya A^{2*}, Akalya S³, Firdhous S⁴, Gokuk M⁵, S Dr.M.Surendra Kumar⁶

¹M.Pharm., Ph.D., HOD, Department of Pharmacy Practice, Senghundhar College of Pharmacy, Kumaramangalam, Tiruchengode, Tamil Nadu, India.

^{2,3,4,5} B.PharmFinal Year, Senghundhar College of Pharmacy, Kumaramangalam, Tiruchengode, Tamil Nadu, India.

⁶M.Pharm., Ph.D., Principal, Senghundhar College of Pharmacy, Kumaramangalam, Tiruchengode, Tamil Nadu, India.

ABSTRAC

Drinking is a major cause of liver disease and is linked to high rates of morbidity and death. Alcohol use, both in terms of quantity and duration, has an impact on the onset and course of alcoholic liver disease (ALD). ALD encompasses a range of liver pathologies, including cirrhosis, fibrosis, and fatty changes. In order to promote alcohol abstinence, slow the advancement of liver fibrosis, and manage problems associated with cirrhosis, such as Hepatocellular carcinoma(HCC), early detection of ALD is crucial. There are several lab tests and questionnaires available to screen for alcohol consumption. Although liver biopsy is still the most reliable diagnostic method for ALD, individuals with suspected ALD are increasingly being evaluated using noninvasive, accurate alternatives, such as hepatic stiffness measurement and other biochemical assays. Determining the severity of AH (**Alcoholic Hepatitis**) through established rating methods is crucial for allocating resources and starting the right kind of therapy. Pentoxifylline and corticosteroids are frequently used to treat AH, however they only slightly increase survival. For individuals with alcoholic cirrhosis, liver transplantation is the most effective treatment available; however, most transplant institutions require a six-month period of alcohol abstinence prior to listing. Additionally, early liver transplantation is becoming more and more popular as a therapeutic option for certain individuals with severe AH. Clinical trials are now being conducted to test many novel targeted treatments for ALD.

KEY WORD:

Alcoholic liver disease, Liver transplantation, Alcoholic cirrhosis, and Alcoholic hepatitis

INTRODUCTION

The alcoholic liver disease (ALD) covers a spectrum of disorders beginning from the fatty liver, progressing at times to alcoholic hepatitis and culminating in alcoholic cirrhosis, which is the most advanced and irreversible form of liver injury related to the consumption of alcohol. Most parts of the world consume alcohol, which is one of the main causes of liver damage. Alcoholic liver disease (ALD) is the primary cause of alcohol-related morbidity and mortality, accounting for nearly 2.5 million deaths annually. [1] In 2023, liver disease caused two million deaths, which is 4% of all deaths worldwide. The most common causes of cirrhosis are alcohol, viral hepatitis, and non-alcoholic fatty liver disease.

Worldwide, patterns of alcohol use varies greatly and are influenced by regional customs and cultures. The most significant factors influencing the likelihood of developing ALD are the length of alcohol consumption and the quantity of alcohol consumed. [2] ALD risk is also influenced by several variables, including obesity, metabolic syndrome, coexisting liver disorders, and cigarette smoking. [3] In addition, a number of factors, such as obesity, metabolic syndrome, concomitant liver diseases, and cigarette smoking, affect the risk of ALD. [4] Women's lower gastric levels of alcohol dehydrogenase, which result in a slower first-pass metabolism of alcohol, have been linked to this gender-specific susceptibility to alcohol hepatotoxicity. Increased intestinal permeability leads to elevated endotoxin levels following alcohol consumption, which in turn triggers more intense oxidative stress and inflammation; 3- A higher body fat percentage decreases the volume of distribution of alcohol. [5] Binge drinking is becoming more common, particularly among youth, and while it is likely to have an impact on the liver, its specific implications on liver disease are yet unclear.

It is crucial to realize that ALD is a spectrum of liver pathology that begins with fatty liver alteration, which is typically asymptomatic and present in nearly all heavy alcohol users. Twenty to forty percent of alcoholics experience fibrosis, ten to twenty percent eventually develop cirrhosis, and one to two percent of those with cirrhosis are annually diagnosed with hepatocellular carcinoma. [6] While fatty liver may usually be reversed by stopping alcohol consumption, other types of ALD often worsen even when abstinence is maintained. Alcoholic hepatitis is a

specifically defined clinical entity that, in its extreme form, can result in up to 50% of patients dying from hepatic decompensation. [4] A major contributing factor to cirrhosis and its aftereffects, such as ascites, portal hypertension, hepatic encephalopathy, spontaneous bacterial peritonitis, variceal hemorrhage, and hepatorenal syndrome, is alcohol consumption. [7] One-third of patients with alcoholic cirrhosis who abstain from alcohol and two-thirds of those who continue to drink will pass away within five years if they decompensate without getting a liver transplant. [8] Hepatocellular carcinoma is the primary cause of death for individuals with cirrhosis, including those with ALD, and its overall frequency is rising. [9]

EPIDEMIOLOGY

2021: There isn't much information about the prevalence of alcoholic liver disease (ALD) in India in 2021, but here's some information about ALD in general and in India:

Prevalence: The global prevalence of ALD is 4.8%, with a higher prevalence in men than Women.

2022

Prevalence: The most common cause of cirrhosis in adults in India is alcohol, accounting for 43.2% of cases. The proportion of alcohol-related cirrhosis has increased significantly over the last three decades.

2023

Prevalence: In general populations, the prevalence of ALD is 3.5%, while it's 51% in groups with alcohol use disorder (AUD). The prevalence of alcohol-associated cirrhosis is 0.3% in general populations, but 12.9% in groups with AUD.

2024: There isn't much information about the ratio of alcoholic liver disease (ALD) in India in 2024, but here's some information about ALD epidemiology in general:

Prevalence: The global prevalence of ALD in the general population is 4.8%. It's higher in males than females, with a prevalence of 2.9% in males and 0.5% in females.

SYMPTOMS [10]

- Yellowing of your skin and eye balls (Jaundice)
- Pain in your upper right abdomen
- Abdominal swelling (Ascites)
- Nausea
- A general sense of feeling unwell (Malaite)
- Disorientation (or) confusion (hepatic encephalopathy)
- Sleepiness

CAUSES

Excessive alcohol consumption, typically over a number of years, is the cause of alcohol-related liver disease (ARLD). Your chance of having ARLD increases with the amount of alcohol you consume beyond the suggested limits.

Although the liver's function is to break down alcohol, it can suffer significant harm if you consume more than it can handle. The ARLD stages are:

- **Alcohol-related fatty liver disease:** The initial stage, when fat builds up in the liver cells. This can happen after drinking too much alcohol for as little as two weeks.
- **Alcohol-related hepatitis:** Can occur if alcohol consumption doesn't stop after the fatty liver stage
- **Alcoholic cirrhosis:** The final phase of ARLD, when the liver cells are severely damaged. .

PATHOGENESIS OF ALD

The precise pathophysiology of ALD is still not fully understood. [11,12] As a direct hepatotoxin, alcohol use initiates a number of metabolic reactions that impact the ultimate hepatotoxic response. [12,13] The current theory holds that alcohol metabolized by the hepatocyte starts a pathogenic process that includes the production of protein-aldehyde adducts, immunologic activity, lipid peroxidation, and cytokine release. This replaces the earlier theory that malnutrition was the primary pathogenic mechanism. [14]

Alcoholism over an extended period of time can cause a variety of liver lesions. The earliest and most prevalent reaction, known as fatty liver (also known as steatosis), occurs in almost 90% of drinkers who have four to five standard drinks per day. Alcohol-induced liver damage can progress to cirrhosis, fibrosis, hepatocellular carcinoma, and even liver inflammation (steatohepatitis) if drinking is sustained. To comprehend alcohol-mediated liver injury, it is essential to comprehend the intricate interplay of multiple unique hepatic cell types. [15,16] The primary processes involved in hepatic liver's architecture after long-term alcohol consumption is determined by the fibrosis that follows.(Figure 1)

Figure.1 Pathogenesis of alcoholic liver disease

The axis between the gut microbiota and the liver was linked to bidirectional actions that involved the integration of genetic, dietary, and environmental factors. The alteration of the intestinal barrier explains the interactions between the gut and the liver and can occasionally have a negative effect on the liver. The intestinal microbes in hepatic disease are primarily linked to alcohol. The gut derivatives establish a mutual reciprocal action that directly enters the liver and results in intestinal secretions. Alcohol-induced microbial peptides raise the concentration of pro inflammatory mediators in the liver's surrounding environment, which is linked to the gut microbiota, the mucous membrane lining, and the epithelium barrier. Alcohol directly affects the liver parenchymal cells during the development of hepatic pathogenesis, which starts the anomalies of intestinal barrier functions, changes the microbiota, and increases the activation of Toll-like receptors (TLRs) in the

liver cells. in particular, how changes in gut microbiota may contribute to the etiology of liver disorders. [17,18]

STAGES OF ALCOHOLIC LIVER DISEASE

The liver is one of the largest and most extraordinary organs in the body as it is a super organ that performs manifold health functions while all other organs have specific or limited functions. The liver's functions include constantly filtering blood as it circulates throughout the body, eliminating toxins and other chemical waste products, and transforming nutrients and medications taken from the digestive system into chemicals that are ready for use. They are following 5 stages of liver disease. [10]

Stage1: Simple fatty liver It happens when fat accumulates in the liver. There is no inflammation or scarring in the liver at this phase. In the early stages, there are no symptoms. About 10–20% of patients with this type of simple fatty liver are known to advance to the next stage.

Stage2: Inflammation Steatohepatitis occurs when the build-up of fat in the liver cells is accompanied with some amount of inflammation. It affects around 5% of the population. If the amount of damage tissues increases the liver may eventually struggle to repair it fast enough

Stage 3: Fibrosis/Scarring If the inflammation seen in stage 1 is left unchecked, the liver tissues slowly start scarring and the scarred tissue starts replacing the healthy liver tissue. The condition is called fibrosis. Here there is a persistence scar tissue in the liver and in the blood vessels around the liver.

Stage 4: Cirrhosis of the liver Cirrhosis of the Liver - At this stage, the scarring is complete and there is no possibility of the liver healing itself now. At this stage the liver stops functioning properly and the symptoms include jaundice where eyes and nails start looking yellow, dull ache in the lower part of the ribs or abdominal distension due to accumulation of fluid in the belly. The person starts losing appetite, weight loss occurs and other organs can get affected like kidneys brain and heart

Stage5: End-stage liver disease (ESLD) There are two types of liver failure: acute, which occurs within 48 to 72 hours and is usually not related to alcohol, and chronic, which develops over time and is frequently brought on by alcohol misuse, uncontrolled diabetes, hypertension, or obesity.

Liver cancer This leads to primary liver cancer, which can occur in the liver at any time for reasons other than liver disease. It is not always the last stage in the sequence; it can also develop during any of the preceding four stages. Just like ESLD, liver cancer is also fatal unless tumour is ablated, resected or liver transplant is done.

SPECTRUM OF ALD

Excessive ethanol intake results in a variety of hepatic diseases, the most common of which are hepatitis, fibrosis/cirrhosis, and fatty liver (steatosis), hepatitis, and fibrosis/cirrhosis [Figure 3]. Over 90% of problem drinkers who have four to five standard drinks a day for decades develop steatosis, the earliest and most prevalent reaction.[19].A standard drink is defined as the amount of alcoholic beverage that contains approximately 0.5 fluid ounces, or about 14 grams, of pure alcohol [Figure 2].

Figure 2

Figure 3

The more severe, inflammatory form of liver damage known as alcoholic hepatitis is typified by the formation of tangled aggregates of insoluble proteins termed Mallory-Denk bodies within hepatocytes, neutrophilic infiltration, and enlarged, dying hepatocytes (also known as ballooning degeneration). The activation of KCs, the resident liver macrophages, is essential to the development of hepatitis.

DIAGNOSIS

For these patients to benefit from additional lifestyle modifications that can slow the progression of their liver disease, early and accurate diagnosis of ALD is crucial.

Patients with Non-alcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH), who have evidence of liver tissue inflammation with hepatocyte injury with or without fibrosis, and those with non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD), who have evidence of hepatic steatosis without a cause for secondary hepatic fat accumulation, must be distinguished from those with ALD. NAFLD/NASH, by definition, denotes a lack of evidence for recent or current alcohol usage. Therefore, recording significant alcohol intake is a first step in evaluating patients with ALD. Aspartate aminotransferase (AST), alanine aminotransferase (ALT), mean corpuscular volume, carbohydrate deficient transferrin (CDT), and gamma glutamyl transferase (GGT) are among the biochemical indicators that have been used for this purpose. [20] The most popular test for assessing chronic alcoholism is GGT, which is quite sensitive; however, CDT is more accurate at identifying daily ethanol consumption.[21] A normal AST:ALT ratio >1.0 can raise AST and ALT, albeit this is not very specific for ALD. [22]

It is critical to assess whether patients with ALD have liver fibrosis and to what extent. Liver biopsy is still the gold standard diagnostic technique for identifying and staging liver fibrosis; nevertheless, it has drawbacks such as cost, sampling mistakes, and variability among observers, which may cause cirrhosis to be understaged. In addition to being extremely uncomfortable, the percutaneous technique has a small but significant risk of bleeding, infection, hemothorax, pneumothorax, and organ puncture. [23]

FibroTest®, a test that includes haptoglobin, GGT, ApoA1, bilirubin, and α 2-macroglobulin, has shown promising diagnostic potential for liver fibrosis in ALD patients. [24] Similar to α 2-macroglobulin, hyaluronic acid, and prothrombin time for a similar level of diagnostic accuracy. [25] Hepascore® integrates hyaluronic acid, age, gender, bilirubin, GGT, and α 2-macroglobulin. These tests had similar diagnostic accuracies for fibrosis (area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUROCs ~0.80) and cirrhosis (AUROCs ~0.90) in patients with ALD, however combining them did not reveal an enhanced diagnostic yield. [26]

The degree of liver fibrosis can be reliably predicted by FibroScan®. When a cutoff value of 17.6 kPa was applied, LSM (**liver stiffness measurement**) with FibroScan® showed a positive predictive value of 91% and a negative predictive value of 92% for the diagnosis of cirrhosis in a prospective analysis of patients with multiple chronic liver disorders, including ALD. [27] A study of patients with ALD who had liver biopsy and LSM concurrently showed good agreement between liver fibrosis and LSM: AUROC of 0.87 for the diagnosis of cirrhosis (cutoff value of 22.6 kPa) and 0.94 for the diagnosis of severe fibrosis. [28]

MANAGEMENT

General therapeutic measures in patients with ALD

Alcohol abstinence is the cornerstone of managing alcoholic liver disease (ALD) at any stage. Research has shown that continuous alcohol consumption can worsen complications of portal hypertension, such as variceal bleeding, and increase portal pressure. Additionally, discontinuing alcohol use can improve fatty liver histology as soon as two weeks after it is stopped. [29,30] According to a new meta-analysis, after at least 1.5 years of alcohol abstinence, the overall survival of alcoholic chronic kidney disease patients dramatically improves.[31] Apart from enhancing health results, alcohol abstinence is mandatory for liver transplantation; the majority of transplant facilities demand a minimum of six months of verified abstinence prior to listing.

The American Association for the Study of Liver Diseases (AASLD) recommends treating vitamin and trace mineral deficiencies (e.g., vitamin A, vitamin D, thiamine, folate, pyridoxine, and zinc) while maintaining a daily intake of 1.2-1.5 g of protein/kg and 35-40 kcal/kg in order to improve nitrogen balance. Protein-calorie malnutrition is a common finding in patients with ALD, so a

careful evaluation of these patients' nutritional status is important and proper nutrition should be stressed. [32]

Alcohol withdrawal syndrome is a serious condition that can complicate chronic alcoholism when patients suddenly decrease or discontinue their alcohol use. Within the first day after alcohol cessation, an increase in heart rate and blood pressure as well as irritability and hyperreflexia can occur. This can progress over the next few days to more severe complications, including seizures and delirium tremens. Benzodiazepines or clomethiazole are typically used to manage alcohol withdrawal, but other agents like gabapentin, clonidine, topiramate and baclofen are also being utilized to avoid the potential side effects of benzodiazepines. [33,34]

Alcoholic liver disease

Excessive alcohol consumption is a global healthcare problem with enormous social, economic, and clinical consequences, accounting for 3.3 million deaths in 2012[35]. Excessive drinking over decades damages nearly every organ in the body. However, the liver sustains the earliest and the greatest degree of tissue injury from excessive drinking because it is the primary site of ethanol metabolism. [36]

Alcoholic hepatitis

A well-defined severe type of ALD that calls for specific medical care is alcoholic hepatitis. The evaluation of disease severity is a key idea in the treatment of alcoholic hepatitis. For this reason, a number of grading systems have been created, and they show a relationship with the patients' clinical outcomes. These include the Glasgow Alcoholic Hepatitis Score (GAHS), the Maddrey discriminant function (mDF), the model for end-stage liver disease (MELD) score, and the ABIC Age, serum bilirubin, INR (**International normalized ratio**), and serum creatinine score. The most popular score is the mDF, which was the first to be created. When the mDF is less than 32, it suggests that the patient has severe alcoholic hepatitis and corticosteroids should be started. [37] A MELD score of 21 is a suitable threshold for starting particular treatments since it has a high sensitivity and specificity for predicting mortality in individuals with alcoholic hepatitis.[38]

Given that 25% of patients with alcoholic hepatitis are infected at the time of admission, infection screening is necessary. Although the use of antibiotics is common in this clinical environment,

there aren't enough randomized clinical trials to support the use of empiric antibiotics in these individuals.[39]

In patients with severe alcoholic hepatitis (defined as a mDF score of ≥ 32), the AASLD advises initiating corticosteroids unless there are contraindications such as sepsis, gastrointestinal bleeding, or hepatorenal syndrome.[32] While randomized clinical trials assessing the benefit of corticosteroids in alcoholic hepatitis produced mixed results regarding survival, several meta-analyses showed that corticosteroid-treated patients with mDF of at least 32 or hepatic encephalopathy had lower mortality rates.[40] For four weeks, either parenteral methylprednisolone 32 mg daily or oral prednisolone 40 mg daily—the active form of prednisone—are given. Using the Lille score, the response to corticosteroids is evaluated after one week of treatment. When a patient's Lille score is greater than 0.45, it indicates a poor response (75% 6-month mortality) and should prompt the cessation of corticosteroids. Crucially, in non-responders (i.e., Lille score >0.56), infections are more likely to happen if corticosteroids are prolonged past the first week. After starting the proper antibiotic treatment, patients with an infection should not be denied access to corticosteroid therapy.[39]

Those with severe alcoholic hepatitis who cannot take corticosteroids can utilize pentoxifylline, an inhibitor of cytokine production that includes TNF- α . The main way that pentoxifylline improves survival in these individuals is by lowering the incidence of hepatorenal syndrome as the cause of death.[41] Pentoxifylline, however, did not show any advantages in patients who did not respond well to corticosteroids at first. [42] Other medications that have been investigated as treatments for alcoholic hepatitis have included infliximab, etanercept, N-acetylcysteine, vitaminE, silymarin, propylthiouracil, colchicine, and oxandrolone; however, none of these have shown any benefit for survival.

LIVER TRANSPLANTATION

For severe ALD, orthotopic liver transplantation (OLT) is one of the most common therapies[43]. Following OLT, the patients' survival was associated with both new cancers and cardiovascular disease. This correlation clearly indicates that the transplant patients smoke cigarettes on a regular

basis. [44] Patients who drink alcohol for an extended period of time may experience multisystemic consequences and related illnesses such myopathy, malnourishment, vitamin shortages, muscle atrophy, and neurological abnormalities. According to clinical research and patient experiences, persons with chronic alcohol misuse should ideally get comprehensive care[45,46].

ALCOHOLIC CIRRHOSIS

The great majority of patients with ALD in clinical practice have advanced fibrosis or cirrhosis, despite the fact that severe AH has a high mortality rate many of the patients are young, making it a crucial area for treatment studies. These patients may show no symptoms at all or exhibit signs of severe liver failure, portal hypertension, or the onset of hepatocellular cancer. since was previously said, the most crucial course of treatment is to achieve and maintain abstinence, since this has been demonstrated to increase survival rates in patients who are both well compensated and decompensated. [47,48]

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